

IsoArch Data Management Plan example

Introduction

This example of a Data Management Plan (DMP) is based on the Science Europe core requirements for DMPs.¹ The answers have been based on isotopic research, and are meant to be used as example text for researchers that would like to share their data in the [IsoArch database](#). **Example answers may be reused when a reference to this template is included** in the DMP (IsoArch Data Management Plan example, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8164911>). **The answers described here are as extensive as possible to cover multiple areas of isotopic research. Answers are particularly relevant for Europe, and may not be applicable in other countries. Therefore, answers should be carefully scanned and checked whether they are applicable to the research project** for which a Data Management Plan must be written. You can make a copy of the [Google document version of the template](#) or adjust the [pdf version](#).

Data Management Plan

General Information

[Administrative information, such as name of applicant, project number, funding programme, and version of DMP]

1 Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

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|-----------|---|---|
| 1a | How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be re-used? | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New isotope data [<i>mention the type of isotope</i>] will be generated using [<i>specify the spectrometer, like TIMS or MC-ICP-MS</i>], which results in tabular data collected in .xls or .csv files. • We may reuse existing isotopic data from scientific literature and/or data provided through the IsoArch database to establish isotopic baselines. All data in the IsoArch database are shared under an open license (CC BY 4.0), so there are no constraints on reuse of the existing data other than citation of the original source. • Sample preparation and procedures are described in detail in an open protocol shared via protocols.io. |
| 1b | What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced? | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data includes the physical samples (bones, teeth, baseline samples), analysis protocols (.txt/.docx/.pdf), analysis scripts (.md, .R), lab notes (.txt/.docx), numeric/tabular data (spreadsheets, .csv/.xlsx). • During and after the project, data will be managed primarily in proprietary file formats (.docx/.xlsx). IsoArch datasets are handled using various open source solutions, including PostgreSQL and SQLite, and data can be exported to .xlsx (data) and .ris (bibliographical information) files. • Where possible, preferred file formats for long-term preservation will be used (such as .csv/.pdf), following guidance by DANS and ADS. • Data derive from [<i>mention the type, chronology and number of sources analysed, like n archaeological/modern individuals and n baseline samples</i>]. • Data are primarily numerical and not expected to be more than 1 GB. |

¹ The core requirements for data management plans were developed as part of the initiative for the voluntary international alignment of research data management requirements, led by Science Europe and the Dutch Research Council (NWO). Detailed information about the initiative is available at <https://www.scienceeurope.org/rdm>

2 Documentation and data quality

2a What metadata and documentation (for example the methodology of data collection and way of organising data) will accompany the data?

- The data will be shared in the disciplinary specific data repository: the IsoArch database (<https://isoarch.eu/database/>). The IsoArch community has endorsed a metadata model that structures the data so that data shared via the IsoArch database are interoperable.
- Metadata provided via the IsoArch database is described in detail in the [IsoArch metadata dictionary](#) and may include:
 - **Site information:** Site name, alternative site name (toponym), country, region, closest town, latitude and longitude, coordinates, altitude, precision of coordinates, distance to the coast,
 - **Source information:** Source type (human, animal, plant and/or organic residues), source reference in accompanying paper, chronology, bibliographical reference.
 - **Human data** will include information about whether the remains were buried, age class, minimum and maximum age estimation, sex estimation, stature, bone preservation level and skeletal representation level. If the remains were buried, information can be provided on the structure number, disposal type, deposition type, inhumation and burial type, container type, body position, body orientation and whether the body was buried in a filled space. The sample type, sampled skeletal/tooth part or type, tooth category and FDI number will be collected.
 - **For animal and plant data** the taxonomy, classification level and details will be provided. For plant data, plant metabolism information is additionally collected.
 - **The isotopic data** includes the sample reference, serial order, result type and number of individuals. For organic samples it includes: $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰VPDB), $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (‰AIR), $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ (‰VCDT), SD, % Col, %C/N/S, C:N, N:S, C:S, ^{14}C dates. For the mineral fractions it can include: $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰VPDB), $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰VPDB), $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰VSMOW), $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰VSMOW), $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$, Sr concentration (ppm), ^{14}C dates.
 - Information on quality control, such as standard measurements, is recorded during the isotopic analyses and in lab journals (of which a digital copy exists so that the data is backed up). A summary of this information will be shared in the accompanying article.
 - Sample preparation and procedures are described in detail in an open protocol shared via protocols.io.

2b What data quality control measures will be used?

- For each batch of samples there will be blanks that go through the same wet lab procedures as an indication of contamination. During sample analysis using mass spectrometry, standards will be analysed (such as NIST SRM 987 for strontium, NIST SRM 981 for lead, VICS and IAEA-603 for oxygen/carbon, [*enter relevant information*]). The strontium data will not be normalised, as this is expected to have minimal effect on the results. %Col, %C/N/S, C:N, N:S, C:S are used as collagen quality criteria for C/N/S data.
 - The carbon/oxygen isotope will be normalised to international standard IAEA-603 and are reported relative to the VPDB standard.
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3 Storage and backup during the research process

- 3a How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?**
- During the course of the research project, all data will be stored on local servers [*list specifications of the storage solution, for example SURFdrive in the Netherlands*] maintained and automatically backed up the ICT services of the institute.
 - Additionally, a manual backup will be made of unpublished data to an external hard drive bi-annually, and a copy of the data will be publicly shared and maintained by the IsoArch database after publication.
 - A consistent file naming convention will be used, using the YYYYMMDD format to chronologically order files, isotopic technique employed ([*O/S/Sr/N*]), and initials of the data collector.
 - Folders will be structured per project and ordered on isotopic technique applied. Samples numbers will be assigned to each individual sample so that information from sample processing can be connected to the eventual digital data. When projects are more extensive, a README file can be used to explain the file naming convention, folder structure and contents of the folders.

- 3b How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?**
- Archaeological isotopic data do not contain sensitive and/or personal data and therefore no additional protection measures are needed in most cases. Some archaeological sites may be at risk of looting and therefore the geographical locations may need to remain approximate when made publicly available.
 - In the case of modern human samples minimal personal information will be collected that is needed to address the research questions (this can include general health status, region of childhood, migration history and year of birth). Strategies for following the GDPR are discussed in 4a.

4 Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

- 4a If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?**
- **Samples from modern individuals and related personal data** will comply with personal data protection laws [*mention for example GDPR*]:
 - [*When this data is processed by EU researchers or collected from EU citizens the GDPR will be followed. Transfer of any personal data outside of the EU is not foreseen, nor will it be shared with third parties.*]
 - An ethical application will be submitted to the institute's human research ethics committee/team where the PI is based. This can include seeking approval for the informed consent for the processing of personal data.
 - Personal data collection will be minimised and only collected to address the research questions (see also 3b).
 - No one outside of the research team will have access to the personal data collected. The personal data will be stored on recommended institutional storage solutions, in compliance with the policies of our research institute. In case of a data breach the legal office of the local institute will be informed.
 - Where possible, data will be pseudonymised (reversible de-identification of the data), or anonymised (data that is no longer personal data as re-identification is no longer possible).
 - More sensitive data will be encrypted for further data security and limited access.
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4b	How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The data will be managed by the individuals collecting/generating the data on behalf of the research institute(s) where the individuals are employed. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Data will be publicly shared using the IsoArch database under a CC-BY 4.0 license, meaning that the only restriction to reuse is attribution to the original dataset. ○ If there is a consortium or multiple project partners, data ownership will be agreed upon in the (consortium) agreement.
4c	What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● All data will be stored according to the rules and regulations of the partner universities and national requirements (see also 4a). ● National, international and institutional codes of conducts will be followed (for example, European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity).
5 Data sharing and long-term preservation		
5a	How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● All data accompanying research publications will be publicly shared via the IsoArch database under a CC-BY 4.0 license, unless the CARE principles need to be followed and the data needs to remain under restricted access to ensure Indigenous control over data. Where data is publicly shared under a CC-BY 4.0 license, there are no restrictions on reuse other than citation/attribution. ● Other data that do not directly lead to publication can also be shared via the IsoArch database, or can remain on institutional storage solutions until used in future publications.
5b	What software is needed to access and use data?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data shared through the IsoArch database can be accessed via a web browser, and downloaded in .xlsx or .csv files after query. No specialised software tools are needed to consult the (meta)data online.
5c	Will a unique and persistent identifier (such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)) be assigned to datasets?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data will be shared via the IsoArch database (see section 2), which assigns persistent identifiers (DOI) to datasets and provides a landing page (https://isoarch.eu/datasets/). The information on the landing page is procured by the data contributor. ● Analysis scripts or software/code generated within the research project will be shared via GitHub/Zenodo. Zenodo assigns a persistent identifier.
6 Data management responsibilities and resources		
6a	Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Principal Investigators are end-responsible for data management tasks, the implementation, and review of this Data Management Plan. They are also responsible for communicating the content of this Data Management Plan to the project members. ● Individuals primarily involved in the daily data management are responsible for daily research data management, as well as adherence to the FAIR and CARE principles. ● In larger projects with multiple Principal Investigators, a coordinator may be involved that can coordinate the data management responsibilities across the partners. ● Decisions on what data are kept and for how long, what data are considered to be underlying the publication are a team decision (with Principal Investigators end responsible). These decisions will be made in accordance with the principles outlined in this Data Management Plan.

- 6b What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?**
- Public sharing in the IsoArch database and exploration of the data stored by the IsoArch database is free of charge.
 - Budget provision for cloud storage, utilising a rented IsoArch instance to securely manage project data, has been included in the grant proposal (*for example, €1000 per year - please reach out to IsoArch to receive a budget estimate*).
 - Membership of all project members for the IsoArch association has been budgeted (individual membership is €25 per year, institutional annual membership is €250), to support the community-driven database.
 - Individuals involved in research data management will need to invest time into ensuring that the data will be managed and shared according to the CARE and FAIR principles.
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